

WAYS TO IMPROVE DISTANCE LEARNING IN KAZAKHSTAN

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This article is devoted to the prospects for the development of distance learning in the Republic of Kazakhstan. It discusses the main methods of distance education. The author considers the conditions of moral and psychological training of students.

Keywords: higher education, distance learning, education in Kazakhstan, management in education.

Distance learning in Kazakhstan is one of the ways to get a higher education without a mandatory daily visit to the university. You can use it to upgrade or acquire a new qualification. People who already have a higher or secondary special education can enter the university. The training period usually lasts from two to three years.

Distance education technology is a promising way to get an education. The creation of an effective distance education system increases the availability of quality education for a significant part of the population, helps to solve the problem of education for people with disabilities and the most complete coverage of the population of the region that does not have the opportunity to receive full-time education.

Advantages of distance learning:

- possibility of simultaneous study in the Republic of Kazakhstan and abroad;
- increasing the number of students with special needs;
- the opportunity to combine training with practical experience in your chosen specialty in the workplace.

One of the priority tasks of higher education in modern conditions is to train a specialist of a new formation who has broad fundamental knowledge, is proactive, and is able to adapt to the changing requirements of the labor market and technology. The introduction of distance learning makes it necessary to change the attitude of the main subjects of the educational system - students and teachers to their activities. The process of transferring the sum of ready-made knowledge is transformed into a process of active, mostly independent search and acquisition of knowledge. Distance learning focuses on independent work, on the formation and implementation of abilities for self-education and self-development. The student is the most active participant in the educational process, and the teacher acts as an organizer, consultant, and supervisor.

Despite the abundance of products and services in the distance learning market, the debate about the value of this approach in comparison with traditional methods and forms of learning still continues [1].

Analysis of the introduction and development of distance learning in modern practice shows that planning, implementation and support of this type of training is fraught with difficulties. They differ depending

on the type of curriculum, the learning needs of students, the purpose of the program, and the speed of assimilation of the entire curriculum.

When using modern IT technologies, students can use not only traditional forms of obtaining information, but also use computer sources that increase their level of independence, get new opportunities for self-improvement, improve and consolidate skills in professional activities. Modern information technologies make it possible to implement new forms and methods of teaching, using various modeling tools for phenomena and processes. Further progress in improving the quality of training of specialists of a new level is possible only with the transition to more advanced technologies based on networked computer tools. Modern society and new IT technologies, which are the foundation of distance learning, place high demands on the level and quality of the educational process [2].

Successful achievement of the training goals of modern specialists is possible only if the following provisions are used:

- accounting for the content of professional activities;
- clear formulation of training tasks;
- providing students with complete and timely feedback on the effectiveness of their training;
- practice;
- maintaining high motivation to learn;
- transfer of acquired managerial knowledge and skills to the working environment;
- accounting for the initial level of knowledge of students.

In the practice of distance learning, five general didactic teaching methods are used:

- information-receptive;
- reproductive;
- problematic.
- heuristic method.
- research [3].

Reproductive and receptive methods are most widely used in the distance learning system. In our opinion, at the working stages of training, it is necessary to increase the role of heuristic and problem-based methods. And at the lecture stages, the research method would be especially interesting.

This method requires the greatest independence and personal activity, teaches you to independently acquire new knowledge and find ways to work based on

previously acquired experience, and this leads to creative search. The functions of teaching in the course of the didactic process are limited to presenting problematic tasks, monitoring the main stages of their solution, providing consulting services at the request of students, checking the reliability of the results obtained by them and evaluating them. Students are required to understand the conditions of the task, independently identify the problems to be solved, plan the stages and methods of research at each of them, and carry out self-control of their activities.

At the working stages, the research method can be used to solve small but holistic search tasks related to studying the content of individual educational questions and requiring passing through the main stages of research activity: observation, problem statement, hypotheses, drawing up a research plan and determining methods for conducting it, implementing the adopted plan, explaining and interpreting the research results as well as developing recommendations for their practical use.

At the final stages of training, the research method should be used in full to master the experience of creative activity and creatively assimilate the educational material of the topic or a larger part of the semantic academic discipline.

The methods of problem presentation, heuristic and research cover the process of problem-based learning. Problem-based learning, in our opinion, should form part of an intensive didactic process in the system of distance learning of students [4].

Didactic teaching tools that are currently used in the Kazakh practice of distance learning are the following: printed, computer and audio - video materials.

In addition to these learning tools, to work more effectively in the distance learning system, you can also offer:

- laboratory remote workshops;
- computer training systems in the usual and multimedia versions;
- databases and knowledge with remote access;
- simulators with remote access.
- electronic libraries with remote access;
- training tools based on expert training systems;
- training tools based on geographic information systems;
- learning tools based on virtual reality.

Psychological problems and the consequences of their application in the educational process remain poorly studied.

In the online version of training, "text" lectures are used (training materials are presented in text form). Further development of this direction is the presentation of the lecture material in the form of hypertext, and the next stage - using hypermedia. For the necessary didactic effect, after the student works with such lectures, it is necessary, in the author's opinion, to conduct consultations and lectures.

The development of special techniques requires remote seminars, which can be conducted via video conferences. TV and video conferences are held after teachers and students have previously adapted to the

new information technologies and psychological and pedagogical training tools used.

Improving the system of control and motivation in the process of distance learning is very important. Control over the assimilation of educational material should be carried out frequently (at least once a week). Exams, term papers, and theses are now held in educational institutions that operate under the distance learning system. We believe that it is advisable to strengthen self-control by using tests. The problem of remote identification of the student's personality is removed by using video telephones and videoconferencing [5].

In the system of distance learning, an important role is assigned to the moral and psychological training of students. Some of them require external guidance to succeed.

One of the most important tasks is how to support the student's desire to complete the training. It is necessary to set time limits for studying the course individually with each student. Reducing the cost of education and improving its quality will contribute to more active involvement of students in the educational process and improve the image of the educational institution [40].

An important factor for delivering this improved content is the creation of a technological infrastructure with sufficient resources for its delivery. Universities should be willing to invest in more sophisticated, resource-intensive equipment and systems to support the changing content landscape.

As already noted, many of these trends are quite real, so the future of distance learning looks promising. Although the industry will still be affected by external circumstances, distance learning technology will certainly be able to adapt quickly to the new environment.

Summarizing all the above, we can draw conclusions:

1. Management activities in the implementation of distance learning are associated with the stages of its implementation and the types of management decisions taken.
2. To solve managerial tasks, it is important to create an information environment of the university.
3. When implementing distance learning, the university administration is faced with the choice of a strategy for its implementation.
4. When introducing new distance learning technologies, the university should choose a model of distance learning.
5. The organizational mechanism for managing distance learning is based on the human factor.

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